

Quality assessment of a country-wide bicycle node network with loop census analysis

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Summary

Bicycle node networks (BNNs) are regional bicycle networks with a wayfinding system of numbered nodes that ease recreational cycling. Implemented country-wide, BNNs are a considerable effort and investment. Despite this investment, planning is a manual ad-hoc process without clear performance metrics that account for the human cycling experience. Here we analyze the around 30000 km long Danish BNN with enriched data, developing and studying such metrics. Via spatial analysis and our loop census tool we find that long-range cyclists can access most of the country, but short-range cyclists cannot.

KEYWORDS: Recreational cycling, Bicycle tourism, Wayfinding, Geospatial Data Science, Network Science

1 Bicycle node networks are underresearched

A bicycle node network (BNN) is a wayfinding system consisting of numbered locations (network nodes) connected via links, Fig. 1a,b. From a cyclist perspective, these are numbered node signs, as in Fig. 1a showing the present node (21) on top, and a fork directing to the next node (24) to the right and to the next node (36) to the left. It usually spans a large region or an entire country. Several countries have implemented BNNs since the 1990s (DKNT, 2021; NodeMapp, 2024; Nederland Fiet-sland, 2023; Province de Luxembourg, 2024) to promote recreational cycling and sustainable cycling tourism, coincidentally decreasing mass tourism's burden on the environment and climate (Kamb et al., 2021; Kim and Michael Hall, 2022). However, planning such an extensive network comes with numerous constraining conditions and millions of potential ways to place the nodes. Despite this

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Figure 1: **Sketch of a bicycle node network (BNN), the enriched data features we have available, and the loop census method.** **a.** A typical node sign **b.** The data set comprises a bicycle network with numbered nodes spanning Denmark, with high-resolution link information such as gradient (red link segments), and points of interest (POIs) from the three categories of facility, service, and attraction (colored dots). POIs are associated to links if they are close enough (gray lines). **c.** For each node i , we construct its loop census \mathcal{L}_i , the set of all round trips, shown here for node 1.

immense complexity, so far the development process of BNNs is entirely manual, requiring years of planning and a large amount of working power and resources.

Despite the international success of the BNN concept, research on BNNs is scarce, in line with rural cycling being heavily understudied in contrast to urban cycling (McAndrews et al., 2018; Kircher et al., 2022; Scappini et al., 2022; Vierø and Szell, 2024). Most literature on cycling tourism and recreational cycling focuses on organizational management, developing attractions and facilities, and only addresses the network design problem through general guidelines (Aschauer et al., 2021; Caspersen and Præsthholm, 2019; DKNT, 2021; Weston et al., 2012; Wirsenius et al., 2021). Meanwhile, most literature on data-driven approaches to bicycle network planning is oriented towards adding protected bicycle infrastructure in urban environments for everyday cycling (Mauttone et al., 2017; Caggiani et al., 2019; Olmos et al., 2020; Szell et al., 2022; Steinacker et al., 2022; Ospina et al., 2022; Diogo Pinto et al., 2026). Therefore, up to this date, BNN planning remains a mostly manual process that requires substantial resources from planners and policy-makers.

2 Methods and Results

Our research integrates geospatial analysis tools with computational methods from network science to provide a BNN assessment based on sound quantitative grounds, on both static and dynamic aspects. Using this setup, we contribute to the field threefold.

Figure 2: **Spatially aggregated properties (first row) and their local clusters (second row)**. Average: **a**. Node density, **b**. Maximum gradient, **c**. Water provision, **d**. POI diversity. Maximum gradient, water provision, and POI diversity are weighted by link length. All properties display spatial heterogeneity. Local clustering (local indicators of spatial association – LISA) of: **e**. Node density, **f**. Maximum gradient, **g**. Water provision, **h**. POI diversity. All properties display several low-low (LL) and high-high (HH) clusters.

2.1 Evaluation of the Danish BNN and its design principles

First, we evaluate the Danish BNN, developed by Dansk Kyst- og Naturturisme (DKNT) and their project partners (DKNT, 2024), checking how its empirical properties are consistent with its stated design principles. We consider the raw network first, fetched from GeoFA (Vybornova et al., 2025), for which we find that most lengths of links and face loops fulfill the design principles of DKNT (2024), but we also find a cluster of too long links (above 10km) and face loops (above 30km) in south west Denmark.

Next we enrich each link with geospatial data on gradients and points of interest (POIs) to allow a filtering of results depending on different scenarios. We use three categories of POIs: facilities, services, and attractions, see Fig. 1b. We match closeby POIs to links and define a *POI diversity*

$D_i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ for each link i as its number of unique POI categories. Further, we make the simplifying assumption that each POI provides a water source, which implies a *water provision* W_i of a link i defined as $W_i = \min(1, D_i)$.

We apply local indicators of spatial association (LISA) (Anselin, 1995) on a hexagonal tessellation with spatial weights defined by contiguity neighborhoods to the spatially aggregated properties of: node density, maximum gradient, water provision, POI diversity. The idea of this spatial analysis is to provide a systematic overview to planners about both changeable properties like node density and unchangeable properties like maximum gradient, allowing to identify both potential areas and obstacles for improvement. We chose hexagonal tessellation due to aggregation on a scale that is both regionally and nationally meaningful, and due to its symmetric neighborhood properties. The results are reported in Fig. 2. Gradients display high spatial clustering due to the country’s natural topology. While gradients are unchangeable, implying a potential obstacle for planning, the distribution of POIs is changeable. For POIs we also find spatial clusters, and more importantly 28% of links that do not feature any POI. A lack of POIs can be problematic, as a water source should be available every 10km according to DKNT’s design principles.

2.2 Developing the loop census

Second, we develop a generally applicable method to assess the quality of a BNN, extending the metrics from our previously developed decision support tool for BNN planning, the `BikeNodePlanner` (Vybornova et al., 2025). We go beyond basic static network properties and spatial features, to also consider the dynamical feature of potential round trips. For this goal, we define each node i ’s *loop census* \mathcal{L}_i as the set of all loops in the network that start and end at node i . This set operationalizes all possible round trips, without repeated links or nodes, and ignoring directionality, that a cyclist can take from node i . See Fig. 1c; shown is the loop census \mathcal{L}_1 for node 1 (red) which consists of the six loops 123, 1234, 124, 1243, 1324, 134.

We found 28,465,546 loops for up to 40 km in the whole network. Henceforth we apply \log_2 to all loop numbers and report these as *loop bits* b , with the idea that the number of loops to choose from, and the forking nature of the paths (where most nodes allow only the decision to go left or right, Fig. 1a), pose a cognitive task that is naturally well described in such information theoretic terms.

2.3 Applying the loop census to diverse users

Third, considering different demographic and cognitive aspects, we investigate three different scenarios of users that would realistically want to use a BNN recreationally. Apart from the “Long-range cyclist” who we assume can tolerate long trips (up to 40km) and high gradients (up to 6%), we consider the “Short-range cyclist”, which could be imagined as a family with small children, who has more restricted length (up to 20km) and gradient limitations (up to 4%), and the “E-cyclist” which can overcome short-range and gradient limitations (Rerat, 2021).

We run the loop census analysis for these three different scenarios of leisure cyclists. We report results for the first two demographic groups in Figs. 3 and 4. We find that long-range cyclists tend

Figure 3: **Loops per node for the scenario “Long-range cyclists”**. Adding restrictions reduces the loops. **a**. Restricted only by loop length 10–40 km allows many round trips in most of the country, **b**. if also restricted by maximum gradient $\leq 6\%$ (red links show $> 6\%$), then 38% of nodes become loopless.

to have abundant choices for round trips in most of the country: Even when considering a maximum gradient limitation of 6%, Fig. 3b, long-range cyclists have loops on 62% of nodes, of those 12% with 8+ loop bits. However, short-range cyclists have few choices without e-bikes: Even without considering the maximum gradient limitation of 4%, Fig. 4a, their loop bits are centered around 1, giving only a few round trip choices on most nodes. With the gradient limitation, Fig. 4b, round trip choices vanish for 79% of all nodes, implying that short-range cyclists have a hard time using the BNN in most of the country. Nevertheless, these results also show that short-range cyclists could overcome these limitations with e-bikes.

3 Limitations and Conclusion

We believe our study, together with the `BikeNodePlanner` tool (Vybornova et al., 2025), is a major first step towards a systematic approach to BNN planning. Being a first step, it comes with several limitations that should be tackled in future work, most importantly: accounting for blind ends which are often connections to important secluded POIs such as scenic views or nature reserves along a coastline; incorporation of traffic safety aspects; accounting for how cyclists arrive at their starting point, connecting with e.g. railway stations.

Generally, our work contributes to fostering sustainable cycling tourism and rural cycling, and our loop census method could have unforeseen applications to spatial networks where the cycle structure is important (Fan et al., 2021), such as optimization of e-bike charging stations (Belotti et al., 2024).

Reproducibility

Code to reproduce the research is available at: <https://github.com/mszell/bikenwloops>

Data are available at: <https://github.com/anastassiavybornova/bike-node-planner-data-denmark>

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Figure 4: **Loops per node for the scenario “Short-range cyclist”**. Adding restrictions reduces the loops. **a.** Restricted only by loop length 5–20 km allows some round trips in most of the country, **b.** if also restricted by maximum gradient $\leq 4\%$ (red links show $> 4\%$), then 79% of nodes become loopless.

Biography

Michael Szell is an Associate Professor at the Networks, Data, and Society (NERDS) research group at the IT University of Copenhagen. Michael is researching sustainable mobility and bicycle networks through network analysis, data science, and data visualization.

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References

- Anselin, L. (1995). Local indicators of spatial association—lisa. *Geographical analysis*, 27(2), 93–115.
- Aschauer, F., Gauster, J., Hartwig, L., Klementsitz, R., Meschik, M., Pfaffenbichler, P., & Wiebke, U. (2021). *Guidelines for sustainable bicycle tourism*. Technical report, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien. Publisher: Zenodo Version Number: Version 1.1 <https://zenodo.org/record/4812801>.
- Belotti, P., Errico, F., Malucelli, F., & Massetti, A. T. (2024). Optimization of e-bike networks. *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 47(6), 922–943.
- Caggiani, L., Camporeale, R., Binetti, M., & Ottomanelli, M. (2019). An urban bikeway network design model for inclusive and equitable transport policies. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 37, 59–66, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2018.12.166> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352146518305210>.
- Caspersen, O. & Præstholt, S. (2019). *Rekreative stier og ruter - Erfaringer fra Tyskland, Holland, Schweiz, UK og Irland*. Technical report, BARK Rådgivning A/S, Copenhagen.
- Diogo Pinto, J., Pinheiro, F. L., & Bação, F. (2026). Frameworks for prioritizing cycling network investments: A systematic literature review. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 35, 101782, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2025.101782> <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2590198225004610>.
- DKNT (2021). *Studie af rekreative netværk i fire europæiske lande*. Technical report, Dansk Kyst- og Naturturisme.
- DKNT (2024). *Metodehåndbog - Kommunal kvalificering af Danmarks rekreative cykelnetværk. Fra planlægningsnetværk til digital visning*. Technical report, Dansk Kyst- og Naturturisme, Aabybro https://www.kystognaturturisme.dk/sites/kystognaturturisme.com/files/2024-05/Metodeh%C3%A5ndbog_bind2_web2.pdf.

- Fan, T., Lü, L., Shi, D., & Zhou, T. (2021). Characterizing cycle structure in complex networks. *Communications Physics*, 4(1), 272.
- Kamb, A., Lundberg, E., Larsson, J., & Nilsson, J. (2021). Potentials for reducing climate impact from tourism transport behavior. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 29(8), 1365–1382, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1855436> <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1855436>.
- Kim, M. J. & Michael Hall, C. (2022). Does active transport create a win-win situation for environmental and human health? The moderating effect of leisure and tourism activity. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 52, 487–498, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2022.08.007> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1447677022001516>.
- Kircher, K., Forward, S., & Wallén Warner, H. (2022). *Cycling in rural areas : an overview of national and international literature*. Statens väg- och transportforskningsinstitut <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:vti:diva-18557>.
- Mauttone, A., Mercadante, G., Rabaza, M., & Toledo, F. (2017). Bicycle network design: model and solution algorithm. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 27, 969–976, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.12.119> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352146517310165>.
- McAndrews, C., Tabatabaie, S., & Litt, J. S. (2018). Motivations and Strategies for Bicycle Planning in Rural, Suburban, and Low-Density Communities: The Need for New Best Practices. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 84(2), 99–111, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2018.1438849> <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2018.1438849>.
- Nederland Fietsland (2023). Knooppuntroutes <https://www.nederlandfietsland.nl/knooppuntroutes/>.
- NodeMapp (2024). Cycling and hiking with nodes <https://www.nodemapp.com/en>.
- Olmos, L. E., et al. (2020). A data science framework for planning the growth of bicycle infrastructures. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 115, 102640, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2020.102640> <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0968090X19306436>.
- Ospina, J. P., Duque, J. C., Botero-Fernández, V., & Montoya, A. (2022). The maximal covering bicycle network design problem. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 159, 222–236, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2022.02.004> <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0965856422000325>.
- Province de Luxembourg (2024). The node-to-node cycling network <https://www.province.luxembourg.be/pointsnoeuds/cycling-node-network>.
- Rérat, P. (2021). The rise of the e-bike: Towards an extension of the practice of cycling? *Mobilities*, 16(3), 423–439.

- Scappini, B., Zucca, V., Meloni, I., & Piras, F. (2022). The regional cycle network of Sardinia: upgrading the accessibility of rural areas through a comprehensive island-wide cycle network. *European Transport Research Review*, *14*(1), 10, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-022-00533-6> <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-022-00533-6>.
- Steinacker, C., Storch, D.-M., Timme, M., & Schröder, M. (2022). Demand-driven design of bicycle infrastructure networks for improved urban bikeability. *Nature Computational Science*, (pp. 1–10)., <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-022-00318-w>. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43588-022-00318-w>.
- Szell, M., Mimar, S., Perlman, T., Ghoshal, G., & Sinatra, R. (2022). Growing urban bicycle networks. *Scientific Reports*, *12*(1), 6765, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10783-y>. Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-022-10783-y>.
- Vierø, A. R. & Szell, M. (2024). Network analysis of the Danish bicycle infrastructure: Bikeability across urban-rural divides. arXiv:2412.06083 [physics] <http://arxiv.org/abs/2412.06083>.
- Vybornova, A., Vierø, A. R., Hansen, K. K., & Szell, M. (2025). Bikenodeplanner: A data-driven decision support tool for bicycle node network planning. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083251355999>.
- Weston, R., Davies, N., Lumsdon, L., & McGrath, P. (2012). *The European Cycle Route Network EuroVelo - Challenges and Opportunities for Sustainable Tourism*. Technical report, European Parliament [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL-TRAN_ET\(2012\)474569](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/IPOL-TRAN_ET(2012)474569).
- Wirsenius, P., Liljehov, A., Petterson, M., & Mattson, F. (2021). *Cykelleder för rekreation och turism*. Technical Report 175, Trafikverket <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1613574&dswid=-660>.